

The prognostic role of Claudin-1 expression in prostatic adenocarcinoma: Immunohistochemical study

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ABSTRACT

The incidence of prostate cancer has increased greatly with the popularization of the prostate-specific antigen test and increasing growth of elderly population. Different expression levels of Claudin-1 have been reported in various tumors including prostate cancer. The aim of this study was to clarify the immunohistochemical expression of Claudin-1 and its associations with clinicopathological data to assess its prognostic role in prostatic adenocarcinoma. The study material consisted of 75 randomly selected prostatic adenocarcinoma and 45 nodular prostatic hyperplasia samples. All cases obtained by transurethral retrograde prostatectomy and were collected from the Pathology Department, Faculty of Medicine, Menoufia University, derived from 2010 to 2015. Overall survival time was available for 51 out of 75 patients. There was a highly statistical significant difference between high Claudin-1 expression and membranocyttoplasmic pattern of expression and low PSA level ($P = 0.005$ and 0.02 respectively), low Gleason score (≤ 6) ($P < 0.000$ and 0.002 respectively) and absence of metastasis ($P = 0.013$ "significant" and < 0.000 respectively). Claudin-1 pattern of expression proved to be the most independent prognostic factor on overall survival of prostatic adenocarcinoma patients ($P = 0.002$) by Multivariate survival analysis. All nodular prostatic hyperplasia cases and normal prostate showed membranous pattern. Claudin-1 is proved to be the most independent prognostic factor on overall survival patients. Also it might be a promising molecular marker for prognosis and therapy in prostatic adenocarcinoma.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Prostate cancer is the sixth most common malignant tumor in Egyptian men [1]. Most of these tumors are adenocarcinoma, and their histological aggressiveness is evaluated by using the Gleason grading system, whereby grades are evaluated according to changes in glandular architecture. Glandular architecture is partly influenced by cellular polarity and cell to cell contacts, and it could thus be hypothesized that changes and dysregulations of proteins mediating cellular contacts might influence the histology and Gleason grade [2].

Basal cells of benign prostate glands are typically p63 positive, whereas malignant glands are usually p63 negative. A rare subset of prostatic adenocarcinoma (PCa) demonstrates aberrant diffuse p63 expression. Strong p63

staining of the tumor cells can obscure the loss of high-molecular-weight cytokeratin when using a cocktail of basal cell markers and create a diagnostic pitfall. The p63 protein has 6 major isoforms; of these, TAp63 and $\Delta Np63$ (p40) are the best characterized N-terminal variants [3].

Claudins are transmembrane proteins and important components of tight junctions (TJs), which are central for the regulation of paracellular permeability and the maintenance of epithelial cell polarity [4]. Their expression is altered in various cancers compared to normal tissues, and Claudin-1, -3, -4 and -7 are among the most frequently dysregulated members of the Claudin family [5]. In addition, TJ proteins are involved in cell proliferation and gene expression by modulating signaling cascades, or by sequestering transcription factors and cell cycle regulators [6].

Claudin-1 is one of the most dysregulated Claudins in human cancers, and it can function as a cancer-promoting and tumor suppressor factor depending on cancer type [7]. Claudin-1 is downregulated in different types of cancers including, invasive breast and liver cancers [8-10] and upregulated in colorectal, gastric, cervical carcinomas and basal type of high-grade invasive ductal breast carcinoma [11-14].

Reduced Claudin-1 expression was associated with increased chemoresistance of epithelial cancer cells [15] suggesting that increased Claudin-1 expression may increase cisplatin sensitivity. Thus, identifying cancer chemoresistance-associated genes or pathways is critical for the successful treatment of cancer [15] also claudins are promising targets for antibody-based therapies [16] and can be used in the treatment of cancer diseases such as colorectal cancer as well in adjuvant as in metastatic setting [17].

The epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) inducing transcription factors Snail and Slug were implicated as potential repressors of Claudin 1 expression. In addition, Claudin-1 was identified as a possible target of β -catenin/Tcf signaling in colorectal carcinogenesis. Cooperation between Snail and LEF-1 transcription factors has been shown to be essential for TGF- β 1-induced EMT associated with loss of Claudin-1 and E-cadherin [7]. The aim of this study was to clarify the immunohistochemical (IHC) expression of Claudin-1 and its associations with clinicopathological data to assess its prognostic role in prostatic adenocarcinoma.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study material consisted of 75 randomly selected prostatic adenocarcinoma samples and non-neoplastic group (45 nodular prostatic hyperplasia (NPH)). All cases obtained by transurethral retrograde prostatectomy (TURP) and were collected from the Pathology Department, Faculty of Medicine, Menoufia University, derived from 2010 to 2015. The mean age \pm standard deviation of carcinoma cases was 60.86 \pm 8.3 Years, median age was 62 and with range of 43-76 years. The diagnosis and the Gleason scoring of carcinoma cases were based on the WHO classification of urological tumors [18]. The Gleason score ranged from 2+2=4 to 5+5=10. PSA (prostate specific antigen) levels, taken preoperatively during the same patient visit, were also recorded. Clinical data, such as metastatic status was collected from patients' records. The main clinical and pathological characteristics of the patients are shown in (Table 1).

2.1. Immunohistochemistry

Paraffin-embedded tissue sections (5 μ m) were deparaffinized in xylene and rehydrated. The sections were treated with 0.01 M citrate buffer, pH 6.0, at 96°C for 8 minutes to unmask

antigenic sites. Endogenous peroxidase was blocked with peroxidase-blocking reagent (Universal LSAB® Dako), using Claudin-1 rabbit monoclonal antibody (Cat. #RB-9209-R7, ready to use, Thermo Scientific, Inc).

Table 1. Clinicopathological characteristics of the patients of prostatic carcinoma.

Variable	No. (%)
Age	
Mean \pm SD	71.04 \pm 8.820
Median	69
Range	56-90
PSA level	
Mean \pm SD	1.869 \pm 1.968
Median	1
Range	4.8-618
PSA level	
4-10	18 (24%)
>10	57 (76%)
Gleason score	
\leq 5	18 (24%)
6	3 (4%)
7	15 (20%)
8	18 (24%)
9	12 (16%)
10	9 (12%)
Gleason score	
\leq 6	21 (28%)
\geq 7	54 (72%)
Distant metastasis (51 cases)	
Absent	15 (29%)
Present	36 (71%)

No: Number; PSA: Prostatic specific antigen

A positive reaction was revealed using the streptavidin-biotin-peroxidase technique (Universal LSAB® Dako) using chromogen DAB. The sections were then counterstained with hematoxylin. Each run contained positive control using specific paraffin-embedded sections of breast carcinoma and negative control slides were made by substituting the primary antibody with non-immune serum.

2.2. Evaluation of Claudin-1 immunohistochemical staining

A predominantly membranous pattern of expression was observed in the epithelial elements for Claudin-1 protein and in intensely stained cells, an accompanying cytoplasmic staining was also observed and according to the pattern of expression cases were divided into membranous, membranocyttoplasmic and cytoplasmic pattern of expression [19]. Immunoreactivity was interpreted without prior knowledge of any of the clinicopathological parameters. The intensity and distribution were considered in the semiquantitative assessment. The intensity of staining was subjectively graded as negative or positive (+1, weak; +2, moderate; +3, intense; +4, strong). Furthermore, the distribution of staining in the

tumor cells was graded as +1 if the distribution of staining was 10% or less in the tumor cells, +2 if it was 10-50%, +3 if it was 50-75% and +4 if it was more than 75%. The same weights were given to the intensity and distribution of staining, and they were divided into low-expression and high-expression groups on the basis of the median value of the sum of these two values [20].

2.3. Overall survival data

By revision of patients' files for prostatic carcinoma cases ranged from 2010 to 2015, overall survival time was available for 51 out of 75 patients.

2.4. Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS "Statistical Package for the Social Sciences" program for windows, version 20, SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA. Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to compare nonparametric data, the chi-squared was used to assess the association between the clinicopathologic parameters and Claudin-1 expression and Kaplan–Meier test was used for survival analysis. $P \leq 0.05$ was considered to indicate statistical significance in all tests.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Claudin-1 immunohistochemical results in the prostatic carcinoma cases

From 75 prostatic carcinomas, 40 (53.3%) showed low expression (Plate 1), whereas 35 (46.7%) showed high expression. Also 32 (42.7%) showed membranocyttoplasmic pattern, whereas 43 (57.3%) showed cytoplasmic pattern of expression (Table 2). There was a highly statistical significant difference between high Claudin-1 expression and membranocyttoplasmic pattern of expression and low PSA level ($P=0.005$ and 0.02 respectively), low Gleason score (≤ 6) ($P < 0.000$ and 0.002 respectively) and absence of metastasis ($P=0.013$ significant and <0.000 respectively) (Tables 2, 3 and 4, Plate 1).

Table 2. Claudin-1 immunohistochemical results in the prostatic carcinoma cases.

Variable	No.	%
Claudin-1 expression		
Low	40	53.3%
High	35	46.7%
Claudin-1 pattern		
Membranocyttoplasmic	32	42.7%
Cytoplasmic	43	57.3%

3.2. Claudin-1 immunohistochemical results in nodular prostatic hyperplasia (NPH) and normal tissue adjacent to carcinoma cases

All nodular prostatic hyperplasia and normal

tissue adjacent to carcinoma cases showed high membranous expression for Claudin-1 (Plate 1).

3.3. Overall survival of patients

By revision of patients' files for prostatic carcinoma overall survival time was available for 51 out of 75 patients. The range of survival time was 1 to 30 months with 11.06 ± 8.610 as mean \pm SD of months and a median of 8 months (Figs. 1-8).

3.4. Univariate survival analysis for prostatic carcinoma cases

Univariate survival analysis revealed the bad prognostic impact of cytoplasmic pattern of Claudin-1 expression ($P < 0.000$), high Gleason score ≥ 7 ($P=0.003$), Gleason score 8 and 9 ($P=0.016$) and presence of distant metastasis ($P=0.006$) on patient outcome.

3.5. Multivariate survival analysis for prostatic carcinoma cases

From the several prognostic factors detected by univariate survival analysis, Claudin-1 pattern of expression proved to be most and first independent prognostic factor on overall survival of prostatic carcinoma patients ($P=0.002$) by Multivariate survival analysis (Table 5).

4. DISCUSSION

This study found that the low expression of Claudin-1 was associated with a high Gleason score, since Gleason score principally associates with the degree of differentiation and glandular formation of tumors, the results are in parallel with the loss of glandular formation and organization of the malignant epithelial tissue. Indirectly it suggests that, in malignant cells, the frequency or organization of tight junctional structures would be diminished. Alternatively, synthesis of such claudins might be abrogated or perhaps expression or activation of MMP might be stronger in tumors with a higher Gleason score. MMPs have been shown to be able to degrade some claudins and occluding [21]. This agreed with Väre *et al.* [2], who reported that the low expression of Claudin-1 and Claudin-5 was strongly correlated with Gleason scores of 7 or higher [2]. Also it agreed also with Sheehan *et al.* [10], who reported that the decreased expression of Claudin-1 and -7 was associated with tumors with histological low differentiation [10]. According to PSA this study found that the PSA value in the groups with a low expression of Claudin-1 was statistically significantly higher than that in the high-expression group and this agreed with Väre *et al.* [2], who reported that in all claudins, the PSA value of the low-expression group (i.e., the group with a low immunohistochemical score) was higher than that of the high-expression group [2]. They stated that the low concentration of Claudin in prostate cancer tissues caused the outflow of more tumor cells, which increased the PSA value.

Table 3. The association between Claudin-1 expression and clinicopathological variables.

Variable	Low expression	High expression	Test	P value
Age				
Mean ± SD	70.65 ± 8.276	71.49 ± 9.507	U= 683.5	0.861
PSA level				
Mean ± SD	2.65 ± 2.279	97.74 ± 9.673	U=370	<0.000**
PSA level				
4-10	3 (16.7%)	15 (83.3%)	Chi square= 12.794	<0.000**
>10	37 (64.9%)	20 (35.1%)		
Gleason score				
≤ 5			Chi square= 13.728	0.017*
6	5 (27.8%)	13 (72.2%)		
7	0 (0%)	3 (100%)		
8	10 (66.7%)	5 (33.3%)		
9	9 (50%)	9 (50%)		
10	9 (75%) 7(77.8%)	3 (25%) 2 (22.2%)		
Grouped Gleason score				
≤ 6			Chi square= 10.215	0.002**
≥ 7	5 (23.8%) 35 (64.8%)	16 (76.2%) 19 (35.2%)		
Distant metastasis (51 cases)				
Absent	3 (20%)	12(80%)	Chi square= 7.161	0.013*
Present	22 (61.1%)	14 (38.9%)		

*: Significant; **: Highly significant; U: Mann-Whitney test
SD: Standard deviation; PSA: Prostatic specific antigen

Table 4. The association between Claudin-1 pattern of expression and clinicopathological variables.

Variable	Membranocyttoplasmic	Cytoplasmic	Test	P value
Age				
Mean ± SD	70.47 ± 10.115	71.47 ± 7.817	U= 634	0.562
PSA level				
Mean ± SD	1.219 ± 1.589	2.354 ± 2.097	U= 421	0.004**
PSA level				
4-10	13 (72.2%)	5 (27.8%)	Chi square= 8.457	0.004**
>10	19 (33.3%)	38 (66.7%)		
Gleason score				
≤ 5	14 (77.8%)	4 (22.2%)	Chi square= 16.338	0.006**
6	2 (66.7%)	1 (33.3%)		
7	6 (40%)	9 (60%)		
8	3 (16.7%)	15 (83.3%)		
9	5 (41.7%)	7 (58.3%)		
10	2 (22.2%)	7 (77.8%)		
Grouped Gleason score				
≤ 6	16 (76.2%)	5 (23.8%)	Chi square= 13.4	<0.000**
≥ 7	16 (29.6%)	38 (70.4%)		
Distant metastasis (51 cases)				
Absent	11 (73.3%)	4(26.7%)	Chi square= 15.3	<0.000**
Present	6 (16.7%)	30 (83.3%)		

*: Significant; **: Highly significant; U: Mann-Whitney test
SD: Standard deviation; PSA: Prostatic specific antigen

Table 5. Multivariate Cox regression analysis for detection of the independent factors affecting patients' overall survival.

Variables	Exp(B)	CI 95% of Exp(B)		P value
		Lower	upper	
Grouped Gleason score	0.866	0.098	7.686	0.897
Gleason score	1.258	0.811	1.952	0.306
Metastasis	1.895	0.306	11.749	0.492
Claudin-1 pattern of expression	7.347	2.032	26.565	0.002**

CI: Confidence interval; **: Highly significant

Fig. 1. Kaplan-Meier overall survival for prostatic carcinoma patients with Gleason score (≤ 6 and ≥ 7) ($P=0.016$ "significant", $\text{Log-Rank}=9.019$).

Fig. 2. Hazard function curve for prostatic carcinoma cases with Gleason score (≤ 6 and ≥ 7) indicating that patients with Gleason score of ≥ 7 were more hazardous.

Fig. 3. Kaplan-Meier overall survival for prostatic carcinoma patients with different Gleason scores ($P=0.003$ "highly significant", $\text{Log-Rank}=13.896$).

Fig. 4. Hazard function curve for prostatic carcinoma cases with different Gleason scores indicating that patients with Gleason score of 8 and 9 were more hazardous.

Fig. 5. Kaplan-Meier overall survival for prostatic carcinoma patients with presence or absence of distant metastasis (P=0.006 "highly significant", Log-Rank=7.469).

Fig. 6. Hazard function curve for prostatic carcinoma cases with presence or absence of distant metastasis indicating that patients with distant metastasis were more hazardous.

Fig. 7. Kaplan-Meier overall survival for prostatic carcinoma patients with different patterns of Claudin-1 expression ($P < 0.000$ "highly significant", Log-Rank=14.063).

Fig. 8. Hazard function curve for prostatic carcinoma cases with different patterns of Claudin-1 expression indicating that patients with cytoplasmic expression were more hazardous.

Furthermore, 61.1% of cases with low expression showed distant metastasis. This could be explained as the main role of members of Claudin family is cell-to-cell adhesion. Therefore it is suggested that decrease in cellular expression of claudins causes increased motility in the tumour cells and invasion [19, 22]. This agreed with Resnick et al. [23], who found that loss of tight junction integrity may be an important step in the development of the metastatic phenotype [23] and disagreed with Sheehan *et al.* [10], who found no correlation of Claudin expression with prognostic factors of prostate cancer, such as T stage, biochemical recurrence, local recurrence, and distant metastasis [10].

Some studies show changes in expression/cellular localization of claudins during tumorigenesis; however, a causal

relationship between Claudin expression/localization and cancer has not been established [24]. The present study revealed that all cases of NPH and normal prostate adjacent to tumor showed membranous staining while all carcinoma cases with low Gleason score showed membranocyttoplasmic staining. Moreover 66.7% of cases with cytoplasmic expression had high PSA level (>10 ng/dl), 70.4% of cases with cytoplasmic expression had high Gleason score and 83.3% of cases with cytoplasmic expression had distant metastasis and this agreed with Dhawan *et al.* [24], who found that a significant linear association between Claudin-1 nuclear, cytoplasmic, or membranous staining and tumor progression but disagreed with him in being the metastatic colon cancer cells expressed the highest levels of Claudin-1 and exhibited the highest rate of cellular mislocalization [24] and this can be

explained by low number of metastatic cases.

Understanding Claudin-1 expression associated with prostate adenocarcinoma may clarify the

response to chemotherapy either increased cisplatin sensitivity in high Claudin-1 expression or may provide a potential therapeutic target for antibody-targeted therapy in low Claudin-1 expression.

Plate 1. (A) A case of normal prostate showing membranous expression of Claudin-1 (IHCx400), (B) A case of nodular prostatic hyperplasia showing membranous expression of Claudin-1 (IHCx400), (C) A case of low grade prostatic carcinoma with high membranocyttoplasmic expression of Claudin-1 (IHCx200), (D) Two cores one showing low grade prostatic carcinoma with high membranocyttoplasmic expression of Claudin-1 and the other core showing nodular prostatic hyperplasia with membranous expression of Claudin-1 (IHCx200), (E) and (F) A case of high grade prostatic carcinoma with low cytoplasmic expression of Claudin-1 (IHCx200).

CONCLUSION

Low Claudin-1 expression was associated with high Gleason score, high PSA level and presence of metastasis. Claudin-1 pattern of expression proved to be the most and the first

independent prognostic factor on overall survival of prostatic carcinoma patients by Multivariate survival analysis. Thus, we think that this specific member of Claudin family is a promising molecular marker for prognosis and therapy in prostatic cancer.

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